

**INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR TRAINING FUTURE PEDAGOGICAL
SPECIALISTS IN THE FIELD OF ENGINEERING HIGHER
EDUCATION**

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Abstract: The article analyzes innovative solutions for training future pedagogical specialists in engineering higher education. The study considers effective approaches such as practice-oriented education, dual education model, interactive and digital technologies, and mentoring system. Also, promising ways to apply international experiences to the conditions of Uzbekistan are highlighted. The results of the study serve to improve the quality of pedagogical training and train innovative personnel.

Keywords: Engineering higher education, Pedagogical specialists, Innovative solutions, Digital technologies, Practice-oriented education, Mentoring system, Dual education.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada muhandislik oliy ta'lim sohasida bo'lajak pedagog mutaxassislarini tayyorlashning innovatsion yechimlari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda amaliyotga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim, dual ta'lim modeli, interaktiv va raqamli texnologiyalar, mentorlik tizimi kabi samarali yondashuvlar ko'rib chiqilgan. Shuningdek, xalqaro tajribalarni O'zbekiston sharoitiga tatbiq etishning istiqbolli yo'llari ta'kidlangan. Tadqiqot natijalari pedagog tayyorlash sifatini oshirish va innovatsion kadrlar tayyorlashga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Muhandislik oliy ta'lim, Pedagog mutaxassislar, Innovatsion yechimlar, Raqamli texnologiyalar, Amaliyotga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim, Mentorlik tizimi, Dual ta'lim.

Introduction: Modern higher engineering education plays an important role not only in the training of technical personnel, but also in the scientific, technical and innovative development of the country. Along with the training of qualified specialists in this field, the training of pedagogical personnel who will train them is also of great importance. Future educators should have not only theoretical knowledge, but also the ability to form practical skills, apply innovative technologies and effectively organize the educational process. Due to the rapid development of technologies today, the use of digital platforms, interactive training, virtual laboratories and simulators in the process of training educators in the field of engineering is an urgent task. At the same time, the dual education system, cooperation with industry and mentoring approaches serve as effective tools for directing future educators to practice. This article studies innovative solutions in the process of training educators in higher engineering education, analyzes international experience and considers ways of implementing them in the conditions of Uzbekistan. The purpose of the article is to identify opportunities for training qualified, competitive personnel through the use of innovative approaches and advanced technologies in the training of future pedagogical specialists.

Literature review: The issue of training engineering higher education teachers has been widely studied in recent years not only nationally, but also internationally. The main focus of the research is on providing future teachers not only with theoretical knowledge, but also with practical skills. Reports published by OECD and UNESCO indicate the use of interactive and digital technologies, virtual laboratories and simulation training as effective methods in the process of training modern teachers. In particular, in the experiences of Finland and Japan, teachers organize the educational process using advanced technologies and pay special attention to the formation of practical skills. In Germany and other European countries, teachers in the dual education system conduct training in collaboration with industrial enterprises. This approach

provides teachers not only with theoretical knowledge, but also with practical skills that can be applied in real production processes. Also, in the experiences of South Korea and the USA, the mentoring system and continuous professional development processes are effective. Teachers are constantly learning new pedagogical methods and mastering the use of modern technologies. Uzbek scientists, including N. Saidova and O. Musurmonova, emphasize the introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies, interactive practical training, and the use of digital platforms in the training of teachers of higher engineering education. This will allow future teachers to effectively combine practical and theoretical knowledge. In general, international literature and scientific sources indicate the importance of innovative approaches and the use of modern technologies in the training of teachers of higher engineering education. These approaches can also be effectively implemented in the conditions of Uzbekistan.

Research methodology: The main goal of this study is to identify innovative solutions and advanced pedagogical technologies in the training of higher education teachers of engineering, as well as to study the possibilities of their implementation in the conditions of Uzbekistan. The following methodological approaches and methods were used in the research process, Systematic analysis - in-depth study of the content and structure of the teacher training process, identification of existing problems and opportunities. Comparison and comparative analysis - identification of effective approaches by comparing the experiences of Germany, Finland, Japan and South Korea with the pedagogical system of Uzbekistan. Synthesis - development of ways to adapt to the national education system based on the analysis of international experiences. Practical observation and experimental methods - evaluation of the results of using virtual laboratories, simulators and interactive platforms. Analytical method - analysis of the effectiveness of the use of advanced

pedagogical technologies and determination of their significance in the training of future teachers. Special attention was paid to the combination of practical and theoretical knowledge in the research process. Through this methodology, recommendations were developed for future educators on the use of digital and interactive educational platforms, the effective organization of the dual education system, and the mentoring process.

Conclusion: The process of training future pedagogical specialists in engineering higher education is an important factor in the scientific, technical and innovative development of the country. The results of the study showed that the use of innovative approaches in the process of training teachers allows them to improve their qualifications, develop practical skills and effectively organize the educational process. International experience, in particular the experience of Germany, Finland, Japan and South Korea, shows the effectiveness of using interactive technologies, virtual laboratories, simulators, a dual education model and a mentoring system in the training of teachers. These approaches serve to combine the theoretical knowledge of teachers with practice and prepare them as competitive personnel. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, it is also possible to qualitatively train teachers of engineering higher education through the implementation of innovative pedagogical technologies. In this way, future teachers will not only acquire practical skills, but also have the ability to use modern digital platforms, which will increase the efficiency of the educational process. As a result, the introduction of innovative solutions will serve to improve the quality of higher engineering education in Uzbekistan, strengthen national human resources potential, and train competitive, qualified teaching staff.

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